

FINANCIAL FRAUD DETECTION- A CASE STUDY OF ADANI ENTERPRISE

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ABSTRACT

On 24th January 2023, Hindernburg Research has published a report on the 7 Key Adani Group Companies that '*How the world's 3rd richest man is pulling the largest con in corporate history*'. It was claimed that Adani Enterprises showed an implied downside in price-earnings by 97.10%, in Price to Sales ratios by 98.13% while in EV to EBITDA ratio by 88.33% compared to Industry Avg. The research also mentioned that entire Adani group companies were put their creditors into danger by using extreme leverages. To check reality and reliability of the report, the researcher has made this research paper on one of the Adani group companies i.e. Adani Enterprises as a case study to detect financial fraud. Many forensic analytics tools such as Beneish M Score Model, Altman Z Score, Markov Chain Model, Benford's Law, ACL-Galvanize etc. have been there in the market. The study is based on Beneish m-score model analysis of a five-year data from the year 2018-19 to 2022-2023. This research concludes that the Beneish M-Score model is accurate in detecting fraud in its financial statements.

KEYWORDS: Financial Fraud; Beneish M-score; Fraud Detection Model; Adani Enterprise

INTRODUCTION

The use of precise and proven fraud detection tools based on financial statements are very much essential for the stakeholders to prevent their returns on invested capital. Not only that but it is also necessary to understand the fidelity of the already published report on fraud detection of some companies by a research firm, especially out-country research centre. sometimes One of the critical issues in current accounting research is the behavior of company managers who tend to submit financial reports that are favorable to their side (Beneish 2001). Recently, numerous acts of fraud and unethical business practices have surprised and flicked the investors. Therefore, an analysis of the facts and figures of a company's financial statements are vital now-a-days. However, there are many different types of analysis that have already been used by security brokers on their platforms. The only need is to learn about some basic fraud detection tools from which it can be identified which are those companies who are involved in doing data manipulation and making false financial statements frequently. One of the fraud detection tools is Beneish M-Score which was developed by Prof. Messod Beneish who published paper called 'The Detection of Earnings Manipulation' in June 1999. It is a mathematical model based on probability which uses eight financial ratios weighted by coefficients to identify whether a company has manipulated its profits.

This model involves several financial ratios to get a specific score to identify the possibility of fraud in preparing the company's financial statements. These ratios include receivable days sales index, gross margin index, asset quality index, grow sales index, depreciation

index, general and administration sales index, leverage index, total accrual to total assets. Based on the score obtained, a company can be categorized as a manipulator and non-manipulator group. The Beneish M-Score itself is a probabilistic model (Beneish 1999).

LITERATURE REVIEW

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RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- ▲ To check the reality and reliability of market reports.
- ▲ To detect fraudulent transaction in an Adani Enterprises
- ▲ To make use of Beneish M-Score model for detecting financial fraud.
- ▲ To analyse the effect of fraudulent transactions on the financial statements of a company.

BENEISH M-SCORE

The model, Beneish M – Score, was developed by Prof. Messod Beneish. The tool is designed to forecast plausible fraud in the company's financial statements. It is formulated with eight ratios to identify the probability of occurrence of fraud or data might have manipulated in income statement and balance sheet of the company (Beneish et al. 2013).

The formula for the Beneish M-Score is as follows:

$$M = (-4.840) + (0,920 \times DSRI) + (0,528 \times GM) + (0,0404 \times AQI) + (0,892 \times SGI) \\ + (0,115 \times DEPI) - (0,172 \times SGAI) + (4,679 \times TATA) - (0,327 \times LVGI)$$

The rule of the formula is if any company can score greater than -2.22 (i.e. a less negative or positive number) there should be a probability of profit manipulation. However, Beneish (2012) in If M-score is less than -1.78, the company is unlikely to be a manipulator. For example, an M-score value of -2.50 suggests a low likelihood of manipulation. If an M-score is greater than -1.78, the company is likely to be a manipulator. For example, an M-score value of -1.50 suggests a high likelihood of manipulation.

The Beneish M-Score formula consists of 8 ratios:

1) DAYS SALES IN RECEIVABLES INDEX (DSRI)

DSRI compares trade receivables to sales generated by the company in one year (t) and the previous year (t-1). If $DSRI > 1$, then this indicates a large increase in receivable days might suggest accelerated revenue recognition to inflate profits. The formula for DSRI is:

$$\frac{\text{Accounts receivables}(t) / \text{Sales}(t)}{\text{Accounts receivable}(t-1) / \text{Sales}(t-1)}$$

2) GROSS MARGIN INDEX (GMI)

GMI is a ratio that measures the level of the company's profitability, where this ratio represents the company's prospects. If $GMI > 1$ indicates a deteriorating gross margin it sends a negative signal about a firm's prospects and creates an incentive to inflate profits.

The Formula for GMI is:

$$\frac{\text{Sales} - \text{COGS} / \text{Sales}(t-1)}{\text{Sales} - \text{COGS} / \text{Sales}(t)}$$

3) ASSET QUALITY INDEX (AQI)

AQI shows the quality of the company's non-current assets that are likely to benefit the company in the future. If $AQI > 1$, this indicates an increase in long term assets other than property plant and equipments, relative to total assets indicates that a firm has potentially increased its involvement in cost deferral to inflate profits. The formula for AQI is:

$$\frac{1 - \text{Current Assets} + \text{PP\&E} + \text{Long Term Invst.} / \text{Total Assets}(t)}{1 - \text{Current Assets} + \text{PP\&E} + \text{Long Term Invst.} / \text{Total Assets}(t-1)}$$

4) SALES GROWTH INDEX (SGI)

SGI is the ratio between sales in year t and sales in year t-1. If $SGI > 1$ indicates high sales growth does not imply manipulation but high growth companies are more likely to commit financial fraud because their financial position and capital needs put pressure on managers to achieve earnings targets. If growth firms face large stock prices losses at the first indication of a slowdown, they may have greater incentives to manipulate earnings. The formula for SGI is:

$$\frac{\text{Sales}(t)}{\text{Sales}(t-1)}$$

5) DEPRECIATION INDEX (DEPI)

The Depreciation Index ratio compares the depreciation expense to fixed assets before depreciation in one year (t) and the previous year (t-1). If $DEPI > 1$ indicates a falling level of depreciation relative to net fixed assets raises the possibility that a firm has revised upwards the estimated useful life of assets, or adopted a new method that is income increasing. The formula for DEPI is:

$$\frac{\text{Depreciation} / \text{Fixed Asset} + \text{Depreciation}(1-t)}{\text{Depreciation} / \text{Fixed Asset} + \text{Depreciation}(t)}$$

6) SALES GENERATION AND ADMINISTRATIVE EXPENSES INDEX (SGAI)

SGAI ratio compares selling, general, and administrative expenses to sales in one year (t) and

the previous year (t-1). If $SGAI > 1$, then this indicates analysts might interpret a disproportionate increase in SG&A relative to sales as a negative signal about a firm's prospects, thereby creating an incentive to inflate profits. And vice versa, if $SGAI < 1$, then this indicates a reduction in a company operating cost or an increase in sales. If $SGAI < 1$, then this means an earning overstatement (Beneish 1999):

$$\frac{SGA\ Expenses / Sales (t)}{SGA\ Expenses / Sales (t - 1)}$$

7) TOTAL ACCRUALS TO TOTAL ASSETS (TATA)

Accrued earnings relate to the increase in recognition of company earnings through additional recognition of revenue. High accrual income indicates that the amount of cash on income generated is low. A high TATA ratio indicates total accruals are calculated as the change in working capital (other than cash) less depreciation relative to total assets. Accruals, or a portion thereof, reflect the extent to which managers make discretionary accounting choices to alter earnings. A higher level of accruals is, therefore, associated with a higher likelihood of profit manipulation. TATA can be calculated with the following formula:

$$\frac{Net\ Income - Operating\ Cash\ Flows (t)}{Total\ Assets}$$

8) LEVERAGE INDEX (LVGI)

LVGI is useful for measuring the level of debt a company has against its total assets from year to year. If $LVGI > 1$, then this indicates leverage is measured as total debt relative to total assets. An increase in leverage creates an incentive to manipulate profits in order to meet debt covenants. If $LVGI > 1$, then this indicates the potential condition of the company for earning overstatement to fulfill its obligations (Beneish 1999). The formula for LVGI is:

$$\frac{CL - Long\ Term\ Obligations / Total\ Assets (t)}{CL - LTO / Total\ Assets (t - 1)}$$

DATA COLLECTION

As this research paper is based on a case study, the data has been mainly collected through the company's website itself. The financial data has been taken from the wall street journal website. For this research purpose, the data analysis has been undertaken on the basis of five years which ranges from accounting year 2018-19 to 2022-23. While The information regarding beneish m-score model has been taken from the research paper published by prof. Messod Beneish himself.

TABLE NO. 1: FINANCIAL DATA OF FIVE ACCOUNTING YEARS OF ADANI ENTERPRISES.

Indicators	Particulars	2022-23	2021-22	2020-21	2019-20	2018-19
Days Sales in Receivables Index	Accounts receivable	12552.88	13712.19	11982.65	13146.53	14307.03
	Sales	136977	69420.18	39537.13	43402.56	40378.66
Gross Margin Index	Cost of Goods Sold	1,05,348.00	54,965.28	33221.64	36415.43	35030.58
AQI	Current Asset	37121	30945.2	19963.31	24182.92	23128.01
	PP&E	67488.88	40338.94	14338.94	13677.89	11510.51
	Long Term Invst.	0	4229.19	5473.43	1897.53	1508.53
	Total Asset	141487	101760	51642.86	46898.36	42536.18
Sales Growth Index						
Depreciation Index	Depreciation	2,436.14	1,247.78	616.58	601.79	1087.25
Sales Generation and Administrative Expenses Index	Selling General and Admin Expense	1877.33	1180.56	349.37	4153.27	2842.23
Total Accruals to Total Assets	Net Income	2472.94	475.37	746.32	798	314.18
	Operating Cash flows	17626	1385.28	4093.53	2453.56	3326.7
Leverage Index	Current Liabilities	44803.05	43849.78	21483.09	23288.88	22509.29
	Long-term obligation	58794.72	30982.04	11249.76	5399.54	4883.18

DATA ANALYSIS

TABLE NO. 2: CALCULATION OF INDICATORS OF FIVE YEARS OF BENEISH M-SCORE

Sr. No.	Indicators	(t)=22-23 & (t-1) =21-22	(t)=21-22 & (t-1) =20-21	(t)=20-21 & (t-1) =19-20	(t)=19-20 & (t-1) =18-19
(i)	Days Sales in Receivables Index	0.464	0.652	1.001	0.855
(ii)	Gross Margin Index	0.902	0.767	1.008	0.823
(iii)	AQI	1.468	2.078	0.906	1.093

(iv)	Sales Growth Index	1.973	1.756	0.911	1.075
(v)	Depreciation Index	0.861	1.374	1.022	2.048
(vi)	Sales Generation and Administrative Expenses Index	0.806	1.925	0.092	1.359
(vii)	Total Accruals to Total Assets	-0.107	-0.009	-0.065	-0.035
(viii)	Leverage Index	-0.782	0.638	0.519	0.921

CHART: 1 COMPARISON OF BENEISH M-SCORE INDICATORS

TABLE NO. 3: DETAILS OF BENEISH M-SCORE

Indicators	(t)=22-23 & (t-1)=21-22	(t)=21-22 & (t-1)=20-21	(t)=20-21 & (t-1)=19-20	(t)=19-20 & (t-1)=18-19
Beneish M-Score	-1.869	-1.853	-2.580	-2.680

CHART – 2: LINE CHART OF BENEISH M-SCORE OF FIVE YEARS

TABLE NO. 4: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF BENEISH M-SCORE

(based on five years of average)

Statistics	DSRI	GMI	AQI	SGI	DEPI	SGAI	TATA	LVGI
Mean	0.743	0.875	1.386	1.429	1.326	1.046	-0.054	0.324
Median	0.753	0.862	1.280	1.415	1.198	1.083	-0.050	0.579
Std. Dev	0.235	0.104	0.517	0.515	0.527	0.783	0.042	0.756
Minimum	0.464	0.767	0.906	0.911	0.861	0.092	-0.107	-0.782
Maximum	1.001	1.008	2.078	1.973	2.048	1.925	-0.009	0.921

TABLE NO. 5: COMPARISON OF BENEISH M-SCORE WITH RULE AND LIKELIHOOD OF DATA MANIPULATION

Indicators	Beneish M-Score	Standard Rule	Interpretation
(t) and (t-1) data	-1.869	< -1.78	the company is unlikely to be a manipulator
(t)=22-23 & (t-1)=21-22	-1.853	< -1.78	the company is unlikely to be a manipulator
(t)=21-22 & (t-1)=20-21	-2.580	< -1.78	the company is unlikely to be a manipulator
(t)=20-21 & (t-1)=19-20	-2.683	< -1.78	the company is unlikely to be a manipulator
On an Average, the company is unlikely to be a manipulator			

TABLE: 5 INDICATOR WISE RESULT ANALYSIS BASED ON RULE OF INDICATOR.

Indicators	DSRI	GMI	AQI	SGI	DEPI	SGAI	TATA	LVGI
Mean	0.743	0.875	1.386	1.429	1.326	1.046	-0.054	0.324
Rule	< 1	< 1	= 1	> 1	= 1	= 1	< 1	< 1
Result	Positive	Positive	Natural	Negative	Natural	Natural	Positive	Positive

INTERPRETATIONS AND FINDINGS

- ▲ As per the Beneish (2012), If Score is less than -1.78, the company is unlikely to be a manipulator and if it is more than -1.78, the company is likely to be a manipulator. Based on the above data analysis, Beneish M-Score of last five years are less than -1.78 which means that Adani Enterprises is unlikely to be a manipulator. It suggests that company have a low probability of data manipulation as far as the DSRI, GMI, AQI, SGI, DEPI, SGAI, TATA, LVGI ratios are concerned.
- ▲ Red colour cell indicates high probability of data manipulation, blue colour cell indicates moderate probability of data manipulation and green colour cell indicates a low probability of data manipulation.
- ▲ Except SGI, the No indicators have been seen negative on an average.
- ▲ DSRI, GMI, TATA and LVGI ratios have been seen positive on average basis of five years data.
- ▲ While the three other ratios i.e. AQI, DEPI and SGAI have been not affecting much to see likelihood of data manipulation in the financial results
- ▲ Individually Year wise only LVGI decreased in the year 2022-23 year
- ▲ While DSRI and DPI has also seen little decreased in the year 2022-23.

CONCLUSION

From the table no. 5 it is easy to understand that out of eight ratios, four ratios are in safe zone and 3 ratios are modest so it can be concluded that majority of ratios are indicating a low likelihood of data manipulation in the financial result of Adani Enterprise. beneish m-score analysis of five years does not support the probability of data manipulation in Adani enterprises. The analysis shows that investors are not been worried with the hindernburg

research report. Even though Adani Enterprises showed a downside in share market, beneish m-score data analysis provides a positive signal to the stakeholders of Adani Enterprise. The Beneish M-Score can detect fraud by 89.5%, meaning that this value is in the high category. So It can be said that the financial reports and financial data is reliable and accurate as far as the Beneish M-Score model is analysed.

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